

ISic0173

I.Sicily inscription 0173

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost, formerly in Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis Manibus
2. Euodia Saluta ri(s) filia vixit an
4. nis III mensi
5. bus II

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

To the Shades of the Underworld. Euodia, daughter of Salutaris; she lived 3 years, 2 months.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175681

EDR 078715

EDCS 10900653

Bibliography

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Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 94

Ferrua, A 1941. *Analecta sicula. Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 264 no.27

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